

DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO THE THEORY OF NATIONAL-CULTURAL ASPECT OF THE CATEGORY OF ADDRESS

Linguistics

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Abstract

The article describes the theory of the category of address in contemporary linguistics and its different views and opinions. It also discusses national-cultural aspect addressing peculiar to Uzbeks as one of the most important parts of human need for language.

Language is a unique mirror of the spirit of the people and the nation. Each language reflects the mentality, spirituality and identity of the nation.

Language is such a powerful weapon that it, along with the life and progress of the society, serves as a criterion for social progress, it reflects, summarizes, and provides the objects and phenomena that have emerged as a result of the society development, as well as their existence.

In modern linguistics, address has always attracted the attention of researchers as a language phenomenon. The scientific achievements of linguists in the first half of the XX century are related to the discovery of grammatical forms that represent the mood of address and to reveal their specific system. Pragmatic factors have helped to differentiate the mood of address, that is, the emergence of different types of address (orders, requests, warnings, prohibitions, permits, etc.). By the end of the XX century, semantic types of address have become the object of separate research.

In linguistics, the category of address is directly related to the human factor and is expressed in terms of social relations, speech activities, communication situations, and national and cultural values. The category of address is related to language development, communicative communication, expression patterns, and features. Address is an integral part of the human speech process. However, the second aspect of the speech process - the undeniable manifestation of conservative, extralinguistic factors - is also related to the address. Current linguistic research focuses on the study of the connection between speech activity and extralinguistic factors that play an important role in the formation and functioning of speech. The address used in the speech is one of the main components of the communication, which reflects the personality of the interlocutor, his or her position in the community, and the interactions of the interviewers. After all, the choice of address by a speaker depends on certain social and psychological factors.

Addressing a person in the process of communication is a very important social event. The address in English has a number of social functions, including: recognition of social status, social

place, and the role of the address in the addressee and addresser's relationships. Address can build on and support interpersonal relationships and, on the contrary, undermine that relationship.

Units of address are used extensively in our daily lives, speech activities - which are widely used in the speech process; it is a powerful, expressive means of expressing the speaker's attitude to the listener, carrying different semantic connotations - semantic "intonations". The speaker draws the attention of the listener through the communication units (forms, expressions), draws attention and motivates them. Forms of addressing express spiritual and cognitive processes directly related to the mood, such as intimacy, sincerity, respect, trust, affection, emphasis, warning, gratitude, satisfaction, love, affection, dissatisfaction, anger.

In our opinion, the address is a complex language unit used in the speech process, which not only draws the attention of the interlocutor to the information provided to him, but also determines the direction of the communication and expresses his or her attitude towards the listener. Address means to draw the attention of the interviewer and say things to him or her, and look for information.

Thinkers of language such as Aristotle, Cicero, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Mahmud Zamakhshari and Alisher Navoi, of course, also commented on the form of communication of the form of address. Specifically, Abu Ali Ibn Sina links the sustainability of society to interpersonal communication, suggesting that people also need to communicate with each other [18. 58].

By nature, address is a social phenomenon. The choice of the form of address is based on certain social factors. Address from different social groups are shaped differently, because the lexical-semantic content of the speaker's choice can be understood by what category of social life he or she belongs to. By the nature of the word chosen by the speaker, the criteria for evaluating the listener's personality may be nouns, pronouns, substantivized adjectives or their equivalent.

Address can also be considered as a means of expressing the relationship between members of society. This linguistic relationship in society reflects human work, his place in production, and therefore the reference helps to define the relationship of the strata in society. The large number of types of address indicate that each social group (class) uses forms of communication that have a specific lexical-semantic character. The choice of the form of address often depends on the existing extralinguistic situations. Some forms of address are fully in line with literary language norms, and some of them reflect speech patterns (such as slenges) that are common in everyday life [4. 32].

Russian scientists such as V.V.Vinogradov, V.V.Babaytseva, L.Y.Maksimov, N.S. Valgina, V.V.Kolesov, L.P. Krysin, A.A. Leontev, A.I. Yefimov, B.M.Golovin, V.D.Bondaletov, V.M. Alpatov, Y.D., Desheriev, N.I. Formanovskaya have done some research on the units of

address and their features and the role of the address in the speech process and gave their opinion [5; 6; 20; 10; 14].

Forms of address are manifested by the inclusion of a number of factors, namely the formation of opposites. One common factor among them is the emotional ability of the address of expressing the feeling of emotion. These feelings reflect the interactions of the interlocutors and serve as a form of communication as a means of expressing them [10. 16].

N.I. Formanovskaya notes that "... with the help of the address unit, the speech is established, the speaker is able to say something to the listener, and the address unit has an appealing function." [19. 116] The address unit is a means of communication that functions not only to "establish contact" but also to "maintain, strengthen, maintain continuity.

Address unit is one of the most basic tools used to communicate people, to set up contact among the subjects of communication, to unite the parties into a holistic process of communication. The address unit is "an indicator that reflects the social relations between the speaker and the listener" [15. 3], "nominal indexing character and discourse operator" [8. 15-17], "a syntactic determinant that shows the listener in the semantic structure of the sentence" [12. 29-30].

The word *обращение* used in Russian linguistics is a term that refers to the concept of the person or subject to which the speaker's speech is addressed in Uzbek linguistics.

The meanings of the word *обращение* in the Uzbek-Russian dictionaries are as follows:

- 1) turning, moving from one state to another;
- 2) treatment, attitude;
- 3) application, appeal;
- 4) use, handling;
- 5) Gram: interjection;
- 6) use.

In Uzbek linguistics, the form of the address in the aspect of nationality has not been separately or specially investigated. In some research works the address is interjection is stated as a general description of the address, lexical-semantic peculiarities, morphological-syntactic expression and structure. The role and methodological features of the address in the speech process have also been investigated in the work of a number of linguists, such as B. Urinboev, A. Abdullaev, L. Abdullaeva [17. 54; 2. 117-143]. The social nature of the message in the context of dialogic speech is addressed in the work of D. Donorov and B. Yuldashev "Literary Language and Artistic Style" [7.190-204], whereas In the scientific researches of S. Muminov and Sh. Iskandarova, the address form is analysed for communication etiquette and stable speech

habits, In the dissertation work of B.H. Rakhmatullaeva, the form of the address in the Uzbek language is investigated in comparison with that of the Russian address form [7. 204]

The means of address are directly related to the linguistic worldview, the level of spirituality, ethics, intelligence, and in particular, the attitude to the reality and the speech culture of speakers [11. 33].

According to the circumstances, communication sometimes begins before the greeting and sometimes after the greetings, starts by addressing to the addressee by calling or referring and it is called address. Not only in Uzbek, but in some languages (Ukrainian, Bulgarian and other Slavic languages) there is a special graphic tool that forms the so-called "vocative case". It is interesting to note that the Bulgarian language has forgotten all the pre-existing compromises and only preserved the "vocative case" [9. 67].

The researcher Z. Akbarova, in her PhD thesis on "Linguistic analysis of address forms in the Uzbek language", explores the social nature of the statement in a sociolinguistic context. It broadly explains the sociolinguistic and psycholinguistic factors of its expression, their classification according to the various signs of the address lexicon, that is, she explores the types of address that are broadly expressed in verbal and nonverbal ways (gestures, colors, different phonics) [3. 65].

The meanings of the word in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language are as follows: «Address» [a] Talking to others, calling, etc.

To address 1) say something to someone for request, calling and referring etc. Илтимос билан мурожаат қилмоқ... 2) look for information. Referring to encyclopedia [16. 402; 13. 320].

So the address is to say, to speak, to invite, to speak, to look for information. Thus, the problem of common address in an informal setting remains open.

The basic and leading functions of each language, as well as the auxiliary functions, are linked to the form of address. As the language lives because of its function, the address is that the interaction of people is the basis for that living, functional nature. The vocative call sentence is a syncretic address: it contains both address and judgment. Judgment is expressed by the various emotions and feelings that are associated with emotion, such as accent, reproach, anger, fury, anger, joy, fear, frustration, complacency. Hence, the sentence so-called vocative in this position is also a syncretic address. It is a special form of address. The essence of the address is, first and foremost, the realization of the expression of one one to oneself, and secondly, the attitude of the someone to another. How this essence arises is its meaning, that is, the meaningful formation of the address.

Address may be made in the speeches of interviewees who are of equal or equally standing in terms of age, profession or position in the society. As a form of address, proper nouns and

common nouns are usually used. They give the speaker some information to the listener. The speaker may use zoonyms, plant or vegetable names, body parts names, abstract nouns to describe the character of the interviewer. According to their function, proper nouns are used for surnames or first names, and in some cases their abbreviated form of affectionate. Person's names are used as the most common onomastic category. The same name can be used in various ways of caressing and diminutive meaning. For example: *Bessie, Liz < Elizabeth; Bob, Robbie < Robert.*

While the address is primarily directed to the listener, the position of the speaker is even higher than that in the addressing process. This is because the speaker chooses the form of communication and the additional means outlined in it and forms the address. Address is a pre-interview communication situation.

The politeness category is one of the central ones in the framework of etiquette-speech communication. From a historical point of view, the phenomenon of politeness originates from forms of address and develops into a system of means of codifying the social status of communication participants and the social distance between them.

The problem of circulation occupies an important place in research on etiquette. N.I. Formanovskaya, for example, considers the address depending on the situation, the social roles of the speakers, based on the idea that speech in a normal situation should be polite. V.I. Karasik considers conversion as a manifestation of etiquette in the language.

The address is directly related to the norms of speech etiquette, since an integral property of speech is its address, its targeted nature. Playing an important role in interpersonal communication, addresses facilitate the interaction of the speaker and the addressee and help create a special communicative space.

The address can be defined as a etiquette speech unit that plays a paramount role in interpersonal communication and creates a special communicative space.

Time, society, social values are changing. Among them, the language is the first to react to change. Choosing an appeal to a stranger - this means giving a name to the person with whom you are communicating, determine your and his status, express your attitude to the future interlocutor. What marker words that refer to the one we are addressing existed and exist in languages now? How does a syntactic unit - address - become a socially significant category? To understand this, it is necessary to comprehend what the peculiarity of the appeal in the studied languages is, what is its history. Addresses can be expressively and emotionally colored, contain an assessment of: болван- clot, остопоп- blockhead, недотепа - blunderer, шалопай - naughty, умница - woman of sense, красавиц - handsome. The peculiarity of such appeals is that they characterize both the addressee and the addressee himself, the degree of his upbringing, attitude to the interlocutor, and emotional state. Consequently, addressing is one of the most important parts of human need for language. Address also serves as a means of obtaining and submitting information.

References

1. Абдуллаев А. Ўзбек тилида экспрессивлик ифодалашнинг синтактик усули. - Т.: Фан, 1987
2. Абдуллаева Л. Лексическая стилистика узбекской художественной литературы. - Т.: Фан, 1979. - С.117-143
3. Акбарова З. Ўзбек тилида мурожаат шакллари ва унинг лисоний тадқиқи: Филол. фанлари номзоди ... дисс. – Тошкент, 2007
4. Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. 2-е изд. — М.: Советская Энциклопедия, 1969. — 608 с.
5. Велтистова А.В. Обращение в современном английском языке (в сопоставлении с русским): Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Ленинград, 1964.
6. Виноградов В.В. Стилистика. Теория поэтической речи. Поэтика. - М.: АН СССР, 1963.
7. Дониёров Х., Йўлдошев Б. Адабий тил ва бадиий стиль. - Т.: Фан, 1988. - 190-204 б
8. Дорофеева И.В. Английское обращение в системе языка и в дискурсе: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Тверь, 2005. – С.15-17
9. Мўминов С.М. Ўзбек мулоқот хулқининг ижтимоий-лисоний хусусиятлари: Филол. фанл. док. ... дисс. – Тошкент, 2000. – Б.67.
10. Оликова М.А. Обращение в современном английском языке (Опыт структурно-семантического и социологического анализа): Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Киев, 1973. – С.16
11. Омонтурдиев А. Тилда мурожаат воситалари // Мулоқот. – Тошкент, 2003. – №1. – Б.33
12. Полонский А. В. Категориальная и функциональная сущность адресатности (на материале русского языка в сопоставлении с польским): Автореф. дис. ... докт. филол. наук. – Орёл, 2000. – С.29-30
13. Раҳматуллаев Ш. Ўзбек тилининг этимологик луғати (туркий сўзлар). – Тошкент: Университет, 2000. – Б.391
14. Ромазанова О.В. Коммуникативно-прагматические аспекты обращения в разноструктурных языках (на материале английского и татарского языков): Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – Казань, 2007. – С.15
15. Рыжова Л.П. Обращение как компонент коммуникативного акта: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. – М.: ИРЯ им. А.С.Пушкина, 1982. – С.3
16. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. Икки томлик. I том. – М., 1981. – С. 482
17. Ўринбоев Б. Сўзлашув нутқи. - Т.: Фан, 1979
18. Фалсафа курсининг айрим масалалари (ўқув-методик ёрдам). - Фарғона, 1996. - 58-бет
19. Формановская Н.И. Культура общения и речевой этикет. – М.: Издательство ИКАР, 2002. – С.116
20. Шаталова И.М. Формы и функции обращения в современном русском языке: Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол.наук. – Минск, 1979.